

Paris-compatible Emission Targets for the Six Major Emitters based on the Extended Smooth Pathway Model (ESPM)¹

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Web apps for this paper:

- Paris-compatible national CO2 budgets: <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info>
- Emission paths: <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>
- National CO2 budgets derived from NDCs: <https://ib-iwp.climate-calculator.info>

Abstract

What territorial emissions targets for the world's six major emitters are achievable while remaining collectively Paris-compatible?

To answer this question, this paper varies key global framework data on the available budget and the sharing mechanism to calculate top-down national emissions targets using the Extended Smooth Pathway Model (ESPM).

The Paris Ratchet Mechanism is based on a bottom-up approach. However, if the national targets are not Paris-compatible in sum, the question arises whether they represent an adequate contribution to the necessary global efforts. An open and transparent discussion of this issue can contribute to NDCs that are Paris-compatible in aggregate.

¹ This paper updates a previous publication in the "Zeitschrift für Umweltpolitik & Umweltrecht" (Sargl, et al., 2021) reflecting newly available data on the remaining global budgets in the Sixth Assessment Report of the IPCC (IPCC, 2021) and emissions data (EDGAR, 2025). A corresponding analysis for Germany and the EU is provided in (Sargl, et al., 2025).

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1 Global CO₂ budgets and their relevance for national targets

CO₂ accumulates in the atmosphere.² If global warming is to keep within certain limits, cumulative CO₂ emissions are therefore decisive (budget property of CO₂). Fig. 1 makes clear what also results from the budget property: the later we act, the earlier we have to achieve emission neutrality and the more we depend on net negative emissions.

The overarching goal in the [Paris Agreement](#) is to hold "the increase in the global average temperature to **well below 2 °C** above pre-industrial levels" and **pursue efforts** "to limit the temperature increase to **1.5 °C** above pre-industrial levels".

For the remaining global CO₂ budgets, the IPCC reports the figures in Tab. 1 in its Sixth Assessment Report 2021:

Warming	Remaining carbon budgets
[°C]	[GtCO ₂ from 2020 on]
1.5	300
1.6	400
1.7	550
1.8	650

Tab. 1: Remaining global CO₂ budgets from 2020 onwards with a compliance probability of 83%³

In 2025, global emissions were estimated at around 42 GtCO₂ (GCP, 2025).

The need to take into account the socio-economic consequences of the pace of decarbonisation, the likelihood of compliance and other uncertainties requires a science-based but ultimately policy decision on the global carbon budget against which nationally determined contributions (NDCs) are set. The IPCC budgets are risk corridors within which political decisions must be made.

If Parties make transparent the underlying global CO₂ budget and its distribution in their NDCs, or are encouraged to do so, this can initiate a discourse that ultimately leads to converging benchmarks for the global framework data that contributes to Paris-compatible NDCs in sum.⁴

² For the sake of simplicity, the subscript "2" in CO₂ is omitted throughout the paper.

³ Tab. 1 is based on Table SPM.2 in the IPCC Sixth Assessment Report (cf. IPCC, 2021). Key IPCC statements on remaining CO₂ budgets are summarised [in](#): (Wolfsteiner, 2025c), where updated data on the remaining CO₂ budget will also be presented. For further background information, we refer to the IPCC report.

⁴ In a landmark decision in 2021, the Federal Constitutional Court in Germany made this clear: Climate policy must be oriented towards remaining CO₂ budgets (cf. BVerfG, 2021). This follows from the physically budget property of CO₂. See also Excursus 1: German Federal Constitutional Court on CO₂ budgets.

Fig. 1: Paris-compatible global emission paths – B650⁵

⁵ All paths adhere to a CO₂ budget of 650 Gt for the period 2020 – 2100. -5 Gt was specified as the possible minimum for emissions. A starting change rate of -0.6% was selected in the RM Scenario Types 3 – 5. For the scenario types used, see Excursus 5. The paths were calculated with [this](#) tool: (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025c). The figures refer to total CO₂ emissions, including land-use change, based on actual values reported by the Global Carbon Project (GCP, 2025).

Here are simplified web apps:

- RM Scenario Types (see Excursus 5): <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>
- Linear global emission paths: <https://global-paths.climate-calculator.info>

2 Calculation of national emission paths with the ESPM

2.1 The Extended Smooth Pathway Model (ESPM)

In order to calculate national emission targets based on global framework data, the Extended Smooth Pathway Model (ESPM) is used. The ESPM proceeds in two steps (cf. Wiegand, et al., 2021; Sargl, et al., 2021):

1. Determining of national budgets
2. Derivation of national emission paths

2.1.1 Determination of national budgets

In order to derive national budgets⁶ from a global budget, an allocation key is needed. In determining the following exemplary national emissions targets, a weighted distribution key was used that takes into account a country's share of global emissions and its share of the world's population in 2019 (cf. Raupach, et al., 2014).⁷ With this two-dimensional distribution key, the current emissions reflect the **current reality** and the population shares address the issue of **climate justice**. This leads to the following **weighting formula**, which determines the allocation of the global CO2 budget to national budgets:

$$B^i = \left(C * \frac{P_{BY}^i}{P_{BY}} + (1 - C) * \frac{E_{BY}^i}{E_{BY}} \right) * B$$

where

- E_{BY} or E_{BY}^i global emissions or emissions of country i in the base year; here: $BY = 2019$
 P_{BY} or P_{BY}^i global population or population of country i in the base year
 B or B^i global CO2 budget or national CO2 budget of the country i ; here from 2020 on
 C weighting of population⁸

There are many possible approaches to allocating a global budget to countries (cf. van der Wijst, et al., 2025). In our view, the distribution key used here represents the most important factors and makes it possible in particular to identify feasible national targets. Other criteria seem to us to make

⁶ This analysis is based on the premise that each country is primarily responsible for the greenhouse gas emissions occurring within its territory, irrespective of the destination of the goods produced or the structure of international value chains. This **territorial responsibility** reflects the accounting framework of the UNFCCC and constitutes a necessary condition for binding national targets and effective compliance mechanisms.

⁷ Some of our tools also allow national budgets determined using alternative approaches to be specified (see Chapter "Tools and further exemplary results").

⁸ Based on converging per capita emissions, an implicit population weighting can be derived in the Regensburg Model (cf. Sargl, et al., 2017; Sargl, et al., 2024a). This represents one possible way of identifying a transparent and traceable reference value (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2024b).

more sense in other contexts (see Excursus 3: Allocation of a global CO₂ budget). A two-dimensional allocation key also has the advantage that only a single free parameter needs to be specified.

2.1.2 Derivation of national emission paths

With the help of the **Regensburg Model Scenario Types** RM 1 – 6, plausible emission paths are derived that comply with the national CO₂ budget. With these scenario types, we offer the entire range of plausible possibilities (see Excursus 5).

A **volume overshoot** can be taken into account in the RM Scenario Types. This refers to a temporary exceedance of the previously defined CO₂ budget. This overshoot is offset by subsequent net negative emissions until 2100.⁹

The potential for net negative emissions is included in the model by a percentage of a country's emissions in 2019.¹⁰ The result represents the potential minimum emissions by 2100. If this value is negative, then a volume overshoot is possible. Accordingly, the more negative this value, the larger the potential overshoot.

The illustrative model pathways P1 – P4 of the IPCC from its 2018 special report can be used as a reference for the potential for a volume overshoot. However, the corresponding values show a wide range. CO₂ emissions in 2100 excluding land-use (AFOLU) relative to corresponding emissions in 2019 range from -55% to +2% (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025c).¹¹

⁹ The following key aspects need to be considered (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e):

- (1) In order to achieve climate neutrality, unavoidable methane and nitrous oxide emissions from agriculture, for example, must be offset by negative CO₂ emissions. These must be provided in addition to the net negative CO₂ emissions assumed here.
- (2) At present, the potential of negative emissions is very uncertain technically, economically and in terms of their durability (cf. SRU, 2020).
- (3) Even if a budget is met that corresponds to the targeted limitation of global warming, a temporary volume overshoot may still trigger the crossing of tipping points in the climate system.
- (4) According to recent findings, “*the century-scale climate–carbon cycle response to a CO₂ removal from the atmosphere is not always equal and opposite to the response to a CO₂ emission*” (IPCC, 2021, p. 9 chapter 5). This potential asymmetry is not taken into account here.

¹⁰ This implies that **countries with substantial current emissions** would have to realise or finance **high net negative CO₂ emissions**. Since a budget for LUC is provided here at global level, negative CO₂ emissions at national level refer to the non-LUC sector.

¹¹ It is important to note that that **net negative emissions** in the IPCC illustrative model paths can also serve to **offset positive emissions of other greenhouse gases** such as methane and nitrous oxide, and not just to offset past CO₂ overshoot.

2.1.3 NDC indicator: *Implicit weighting of the population (IWP)*

Through their NDCs, countries implicitly indicate the national CO2 budget they claim for the future. The implicit weighting of the population ([IWP](#)) is a helpful measure for assessing this claim (cf. Sargl, et al., 2024a; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2024b; Wolfsteiner, 2025b). If this national budget can be [estimated](#) (cf. Wolfsteiner, 2025a) or, at best, is even directly specified, the implicit weighting of the population depending on a global CO2 budget is given by

$$C = \frac{B^i - B^* E_{BY}^i / E_{BY}}{B^* (P_{BY}^i / P_{BY} - E_{BY}^i / E_{BY})} = IWP$$

after transforming the above weighting formula.

See Tab. 6 for the IWP for the six major emitters based on their NDCs.

2.2 Data basis used

The EU database EDGAR provides CO₂ emissions excluding CO₂ emissions from land-use (LUC) and international shipping and aviation (ISA) for all countries in the world which are shown in Tab. 2 for the six largest emitters plus Nigeria (cf. EDGAR, 2025).¹² For comparison Nigeria is added as an example of a country with low per capita emissions and a low share of global emissions.

	emissions in Gt				per capita 2019 in t	share in global emissions 2019	share in global population 2019
	1990	2010	2019	2024			
China	2.4	9.1	11.8	13.1	8.3	32%	18%
United States	5.0	5.5	5.0	4.6	15.1	14%	4%
EU27	3.8	3.4	2.9	2.5	6.6	8%	6%
India	0.6	1.7	2.6	3.2	1.9	7%	18%
Russia	2.4	1.7	1.9	2.0	12.9	5%	2%
Japan	1.2	1.2	1.1	1.0	8.9	3%	2%
Sum	15.4	22.7	25.2	26.4		69%	50%
Nigeria	0.08	0.09	0.13	0.13	0.6	0.3%	2.6%
Global	22.0	32.8	36.7	39.6	4.8	100%	

Tab. 2: Baseline data of the six largest emitters plus Nigeria¹³

¹² Brief description of different concepts of CO₂ emissions from land use:

- GCP LUC = CO₂ from land-use changes
- IPCC AFOLU = agriculture + forestry + land-use
- UNFCCC/EU LULUCF = essentially CO₂ from land-use and forests

AFOLU and LULUCF are almost identical with respect to gross CO₂ fluxes, as agriculture largely consists of CH₄/N₂O.

When using the remaining carbon budgets presented by the IPCC, it is important to offset all anthropogenic CO₂ emissions. This includes not only emissions from fossil fuels and industrial processes (EFOS), but also emissions from land-use changes.

The Global Carbon Project (GCP) LUC category is the appropriate measure to be used here (GCP, 2025), because AFOLU-CO₂ (IPCC) and LULUCF (UNFCCC/EU) include not only land-use changes but also management-related sinks (e.g. forest management, wood products). These sinks are already accounted for in the IPCC budget framework as part of the natural land sink.

However, in the IPCC illustrative model paths, AFOLU CO₂ emissions only reflect sources from land-use changes (cf. IPCC, 2019, sec. 2.3.1.2). Management-related sinks (forests, soils, HWP) are reported separately as land sinks. Therefore, LUC according to GCP largely corresponds to AFOLU emissions in the IPCC illustrative model paths.

The following are the estimated emissions for 2010:

concept	model path IPCC SR15	GtCO ₂	source
LUC		+6.5	(GCP, 2025)
LULUCF		-2.6	(EDGAR, 2025)
AFOLU IPCC SR15	P1	+5.4	(Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025c)
	P2	+4.6	
	P3	+7.2	
	P4	+4.2	

¹³ These figures refer to CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel use (except international shipping and aviation; ISA) and cement production (EDGAR, 2025). CO₂ emissions from land-use change (LUC) are therefore not included here (see also Chapter 2.2 Data basis used). Note: The countries (excluding the EU) that account for less than 2% of global CO₂ emissions are together responsible for around 39% of global emissions. This implies that countries with relatively small individual emission shares collectively contribute a substantial fraction of global emissions.

Before calculating national budgets on this data basis, global budgets for LUC and ISA emissions must be deducted from the global budget (see exemplary calculations in Tab. 3).¹⁴ The national budgets derived from this global CO₂ budget thus cover CO₂ emissions from fossil fuel use (except ISA) and cement production.

For the LUC budget, the illustrative model paths P1 - P4 of the IPCC from its Special Report 2018 could be used as a reference. However, the cumulative AFOLU emissions there range from -230 Gt to +140 Gt for the period 2020 - 2100 (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025c; Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e).¹⁵

However, it is problematic when it is not clear who is responsible for ensuring that the LUC budget is actually adhered to. Moreover, there are major doubts about the permanence of negative LUC emissions.¹⁶

Further a budget of 3.3% of the global budget is reserved for ISA, which corresponds roughly to its current share of global CO₂ emissions.¹⁷

	Gt	Gt	Gt
LUC budget 2020 – 2100	-100	0	100
global CO₂ budget 2020 - 2100	550	550	550
- LUC budget 2020 - 2100	-100	0	100
- ISA budget 2020 - 2100	18	18	18
= global CO ₂ budget 2020 - 2100 to be distributed	632	532	432

Tab. 3: Calculation scheme of the global budget to be distributed here¹⁸

¹⁴ If country-level data including LUC and ISA are available, this step is not necessary (cf. Sargl, et al., 2025). However, especially in the case of LUC emissions, there are still substantial uncertainties in determining the level of emissions. If estimates were used here, with a wide range in accuracy, this could significantly distort the results. For example, GCP uses three sources for national LUC emissions. For 2019, the figures for the EU are -14.3, -0.8 and +6.4 Mt (GCP, 2025).

¹⁵ For a discussion of the **limitations**, see Footnotes 11 and 12.

¹⁶ For example, reforestation may not be permanent under climate change.

¹⁷ Global ISA emissions are estimated at 1.3 GtCO₂ in 2019 (EDGAR, 2025). In the Excel tool used here (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025b), other values for ISA emissions can also be specified.

¹⁸ Example calculation for the second column: 550 minus (-100) minus (+18) equals 632.

3 Current emission targets of the six largest emitters

Tab. 4 shows the current status of already submitted NDCs of the six largest emitters, which together account for about 70% of global emissions (cf. Tab. 2).

country	emissions	target year 2030	target year 2035	target year 2040	reference year	long-term goals
United States ¹⁹	all sectors and all gases	-50% to -52%	-61% to -66%	-	2005	climate neutrality by 2050
EU27	including LU-LUCF and international aviation	-55%	-66% to -72%	-85% to -90% ²⁰	1990	
Japan	including land-use & forests	-46%	-60%	-	2013	
India	excluding LULUCF	reduce emission intensity 45% in relation to the national product	-	-	2005	net zero 2070
Russia	GHG, taking into account the maximum possible absorptive capacity of forests.	-30%	-35% to -33%	-	1990	net zero 2060
China	all GHGs	peak year before 2030	-7% to -10%	-	peak year	climate neutrality before 2060

Tab. 4: Current emission targets of the six largest emitters²¹

For the purpose of comparison, Tab. 5 shows the targets converted into the change in emissions in 2030 compared to 2019. However, this neglects the fact that NDCs can refer to different greenhouse gas fractions (see Chapter 2.2 Data basis used).

¹⁹ The renewed withdrawal of the United States from the Paris Agreement under the Trump administration is scheduled to take effect on 27 January 2026.

²⁰ As of 6 December 2025: The EU has reached a political agreement — though not yet formalised in legislation — a 2040 climate target of a 90% net GHG reduction relative to 1990 levels, of which up to 5 percentage points may be met through high-quality international mitigation outside the EU. This implies a minimum 85% domestic reduction within the Union.

²¹ Source and further details are available from the [Climate Action Tracker](#) (status as of 12 January 2026).

country	target year 2030	reference year	change 2030 vs. 2019
China	see assumption footnote 22		+11%
United States	-50%	2005	-41%
EU27	-55%	1990	-41%
India	see assumption footnote 22		+18%
Russia	-30%	1990	-8%
Japan	-46%	2013	-36%

Tab. 5: Conversion NDCs to the change in 2030 compared to 2019²²

The question arises, if these commitments are sufficient to meet the Paris climate targets, especially for the target years 2030 and 2035. Due to the budgetary nature of CO₂, the coming years are crucial to keeping the Paris climate targets within reach. Our way to answer this question is to calculate national emission targets as reference values that arise top-down given different global framework data.

An initial impression can be gained by looking at the implicit weighting of the population (see Chapter 2.1.3 NDC indicator: Implicit weighting of the population (IWP)).

Tab. 6 shows the implicit weighting of the population (IWP) based on an estimated implicit national emission budget. For the estimation of the implicit budget, linear emission paths from 2025 to 2030 and from 2031 to the year of emissions neutrality were assumed.²³ Our web app <https://IB-IWP.climate-calculator.info> can perform this calculation for any country in the world, provided that the necessary data can be derived from the NDC.

²² Assumptions:

- China:
 - Emissions increase by 0.8% p.a. in the years 2025, 2026, ..., 2030. 0.8% is the actual value in 2024.
 - The resulting figure for 2030 has been reduced by 5% reflecting China's stated intention to reach its peak before 2030.
- India:
 - GDP will increase by 6% p.a. in the years 2024, 2025, ..., 2030. Actual value 2024: 6.5%.
 - India's GDP was derived from the "CO₂ emissions per GDP" according to (EDGAR, 2025).

The assumptions can be adjusted in the web apps <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info/> and <https://ib-iwp.climate-calculator.info>.

Note: The NDCs in Tab. 4 refer in part to different greenhouse gas fractions. For the sake of simplicity, it is assumed here that all greenhouse gas fractions are to be reduced proportionally.

²³ The two linear emission pathways represent a significant simplification. For example, they do not account for whether net negative emissions are planned after reaching emissions neutrality in order to compensate for a previous overshoot. In addition, other scenario types (see Excursus 5: Regensburg Model Scenario Types) would result in slightly different budgets.

	target 2030 vs. 2019	net zero tar- get	implicit budget	IWP	IWP
				<i>BY: 2019</i>	<i>BY: 2019</i>
				<i>GB: 650 Gt</i>	<i>GB: 550 Gt</i>
				Gt	Gt
China	11%	2060	332	-150%	-219%
United States	-41%	2050	73	21%	-2%
EU27	-41%	2050	42	60%	4%
India	18%	2070	91	70%	94%
Russia	-8%	2060	45	-67%	-108%
Japan	-36%	2050	17	26%	-9%
sum			600		

Tab. 6: *Implicit budgets and weightings population (IWP)*²⁴

Tab. 6 shows that even grandfathering is not sufficient to reflect the NDCs for China and Russia in this framework. With a remaining global budget (*GB*) of 650 Gt from 2020 onwards, China's current emissions would need to be weighted at +250%, while its population would effectively receive a negative weighting of -150%.²⁵

²⁴ A share of 3.3% was reserved for ISA emissions, and a zero budget was assumed for LUC.

²⁵ Negative values of the implicit weighting of the population (IWP) do not indicate a **technical** or **mathematical** inconsistency, but rather a structural incompatibility. Rather, they occur when the national CO₂ budget implicitly claimed by an NDC exceeds the country's share of a given global CO₂ budget even under pure grandfathering. In this case, population weighting would need to become negative to reconcile the claimed national budget with the global constraint. Such values therefore signal a structural incompatibility between the NDC and the assumed global CO₂ budget.

For China, negative IWP values reflect the combination of a very high current emissions share, a comparatively late neutrality target, and the severely constrained remaining global CO₂ budget.

4 Exemplary national emission targets for the six largest emitters plus Nigeria

Exemplary national emission targets are calculated, with the following global framework data being varied:

- (1) Global CO₂ budget 2020 - 2100
- (2) Weighting of the population in the determination of national CO₂ budgets
- (3) Inclusion of a national volume overshoot in the non-LUC sector
- (4) Inclusion of a negative global LUC budget

The following results can be reproduced with our web apps:

- Determination of national CO₂ budgets: <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info/>. Many other combinations of global framework data can also be specified there. The tool also provides the results for a linear emission path.
- Determining emission paths using the RM Scenario Types: <https://paths.climate-calculator.info>.

The following results were determined using [this](#) detailed Excel tool: (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025b).

Note: The NDCs in Tab. 4 refer in part to different greenhouse gas fractions. Therefore, the reference values calculated in this chapter are only comparable to a limited extent if the greenhouse gas fractions are to be reduced to varying degrees.

4.1 Overview of results for extreme and mean values in the global framework data

The following results are based on a linear course of the emission paths (scenario type: RM-6).²⁶

A zero LUC budget and 0% potential for net negative emissions are assumed at the start.²⁷

According to the IPCC report, 300 GtCO₂ from 2020 onwards corresponds with a probability of 83% with compliance with the 1.5 °C limit (see Tab. 1). Due to the historical responsibility of the "old" industrialized countries for past emissions, much can be said for dividing a remaining global

²⁶ Due to the inclusion of observed emissions for the years 2020 – 2024, the emission pathways follow a straight line only from 2025 onwards (see Fig. 2).

²⁷ A LUC budget of zero means that annual positive net LUC emissions are fully compensated by annual negative net LUC emissions over the period up to 2100. A net negative emissions potential of 0% implies that the minimum value of the emission pathway is zero. This does not take into account whether a negative LUC-CO₂ budget or net negative CO₂ emissions without land-use are also required to offset other positive greenhouse gas emissions (see also Footnote 11).

In the Excel tool used (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025b), alternative values can also be specified.

CO2 budget among the countries according to their population size respectively per capita (weighting population: 100%). This would lead to the emission targets in Tab. 7. Using a global CO2 budget of 650 Gt, which corresponds to keeping warming to 1.8 °C, leads to the results in Tab. 8.

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					300	minimum annual emissions			0%
weighting population					100%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt			0
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality	
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040					
reference year:	1990	2019							
China	-	-	-	-	53	5	-	-	
United States	-	-	-	-	12	2	-	-	
EU27	-100%	-100%	-100%	-100%	17	6	0.0	2028	
India	298%	-6%	-31%	-56%	51	20	0.0	2049	
Russia	-	-	-	-	5	3	-	-	
Japan	-	-	-	-	5	4	-	-	
Nigeria	67%	0%	-5%	-9%	8	60	0.0	-	

Tab. 7: Linear emission paths - reference values big six - B300 / P100 / NNE0 / LUC0²⁸

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					650	minimum annual emissions			0%
weighting population					100%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt			0
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality	
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040					
reference year:	1990	2019							
China	82%	-63%	-100%	-100%	116	10	0.0	2034	
United States	-100%	-100%	-100%	-100%	27	5	0.0	2027	
EU27	-55%	-41%	-63%	-84%	36	12	0.0	2044	
India	375%	12%	2%	-8%	112	44	0.0	2087	
Russia	-100%	-100%	-100%	-100%	12	6	0.0	2028	
Japan	-59%	-58%	-95%	-100%	10	9	0.0	2036	
Nigeria	91%	14%	22%	29%	16	130	0.0	-	

Tab. 8: Linear emission paths - reference values big six - B650 / P100 / NNE0 / LUC0

The framework data used, and in particular the 100% population weighting, obviously no longer lead to realisable targets for the territorial emissions of China, the USA, Russia and Japan, even if the target is reduced to 1.8 °C, which can be understood as the lower limit of the Paris Agreement.

²⁸ Structure of the reference value tables based on linear emission pathways:

For the target years, the change in emissions reported as a percentage relative to the reference years is given for a linear emission path.

The percentage given for the minimum annual emissions is applied to the country's emissions in 2019. The result represents the possible minimum of the country's emissions up to 2100. A temporary overshoot is possible if this minimum is negative.

The national CO2 budget for the period 2020 - 2100 results from applying the weighted distribution key to the global CO2 budget to be distributed here (see calculation logic Tab. 3).

The scope in years is obtained by dividing the national CO2 budget by the country's emissions in 2019 (see Tab. 2).

The year of emissions neutrality is the first year in which emissions become zero or negative. If no year is reported, emissions neutrality is not achieved by 2100 or can no longer be achieved in compliance with the specified framework data due to actual emissions after 2019.

With a global CO2 budget that is seriously geared towards limiting global warming to 1.5 °C, China, USA, Russia and Japan would no longer be able to meet their budget due to their actual emissions since 2019 (see Tab. 7).

Weighting the factors *population* and *emissions* equally leads to the results in Tab. 9 and the results of a population weighting of 0% (grandfathering) are shown in Tab. 10.

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					650	minimum annual emissions		0%
weighting population					50%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt		0
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040				
reference year:	1990	2019						
China	235%	-32%	-67%	-100%	159	13	0.0	2040
United States	-44%	-44%	-75%	-100%	56	11	0.0	2040
EU27	-51%	-35%	-52%	-69%	43	15	0.0	2050
India	349%	6%	-9%	-24%	78	30	0.0	2066
Russia	-55%	-41%	-82%	-100%	22	12	0.0	2038
Japan	-40%	-38%	-59%	-80%	15	13	0.0	2045
Nigeria	72%	2%	0%	-1%	9	74	0.0	-

Tab. 9: Linear emission paths - reference values big six - B650 / P50 / NNE0 / LUC0²⁹

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					650	minimum annual emissions		0%
weighting population					0%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt		0
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040				
reference year:	1990	2019						
China	297%	-19%	-44%	-69%	203	17	0.0	2047
United States	-27%	-27%	-44%	-61%	85	17	0.0	2052
EU27	-48%	-32%	-46%	-59%	50	17	0.0	2055
India	267%	-14%	-45%	-76%	44	17	0.0	2044
Russia	-39%	-20%	-43%	-67%	32	17	0.0	2048
Japan	-33%	-31%	-45%	-60%	19	17	0.0	2055
Nigeria	32%	-21%	-43%	-65%	2	17	0.0	2049

Tab. 10: Linear emission paths - reference values big six - B650 / P0 / NNE0 / LUC0³⁰

Weighting the population with 50% instead of 100% would mean a higher ambition level for India, since among the six largest emitters, only India's per capita emissions in the base year 2019 are below the global average (see Tab. 2). For the other five, however, the requirements are reduced (see also Fig. 3).

²⁹ Tab. 27 in the appendix illustrates the 60 largest national CO2 budgets resulting from these framework data.

³⁰ Note: If the population share is neglected and observed emissions for the years 2020 – 2024 are not taken into account (see Footnote 26), grandfathering would result in identical targets for all countries.

Fig. 2 shows the emission paths for the six largest emitters with a global CO2 budget of 650 Gt and a population weighting of 50%. The figure also illustrates that, for China, a structural incompatibility between China’s emissions pathway and Paris-compatible global CO2 budget constraints becomes evident that cannot easily be offset by additional reductions elsewhere.

Fig. 2: Emission paths major emitters (RM-6-abs) – B650 / P50 / NNE0 / LUC0³¹

Fig. 3 shows the course of the reference values 2030 to 2019 depending on the weighting of the population with a global CO2 budget of 650 Gt.

³¹ Actual emissions 2010 - 2024 (see also Footnote 26).

Fig. 3: Weighting population vs. targets 2030/2019 major emitters – B650 / NNE0 / LUC0³²

Tab. 11 considers a potential for net negative emissions (and thus for an overshoot) of -25% and a LUC budget of -180 Gt. These figures are based on the illustrative model path P3 from the IPCC Special Report 2018 (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e).³³ However, relying so heavily on negative CO2 emissions harbours massive risks.³⁴

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					650	minimum annual emissions		-25%
weighting population					50%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt		-180
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040				
reference year:	1990	2019						
China	358%	-6%	-21%	-36%	205	17	101.1	2062
United States	-21%	-21%	-33%	-45%	72	14	39.8	2064
EU27	-43%	-26%	-35%	-44%	55	19	15.6	2072
India	372%	11%	1%	-9%	100	39	6.8	2084
Russia	-31%	-10%	-25%	-40%	28	15	16.8	2061
Japan	-28%	-25%	-35%	-45%	19	17	7.2	2069
Nigeria	79%	7%	8%	10%	12	95	0.0	-

Tab. 11: Linear emission paths - reference values big six - B650 / P50 / NNE25 / LUC180

³² Without taking actual emissions after 2019 into account, all countries would start from the same value with a population weighting of 0% (grandfathering).

³³ See the **limitations** described in Footnote 11.

³⁴ See Footnote 9 and (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e).

4.2 Exemplary global framework data reflect the NDCs of USA, EU and Japan

The following exemplary combinations of the global framework data in Tab. 12 lead to results that come close to the targets in the NDCs of the USA, the EU and Japan for 2030 (see Tab. 13). Due to the limitations associated with negative CO₂ emissions, conservative assumptions were made for the LUC budget and potential of net negative emissions (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e). Population weighting was used as a free parameter to map the NDCs for 2030 of the countries considered here as closely as possible.

global CO ₂ budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt					550	minimum annual emissions			-2%
weighting population					15%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt			0
reference values (linear emission paths, RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality	
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040					
reference year:	1990	2019							
China	261%	-26%	-57%	-88%	160	14	13.8	2042	
United States	-33%	-33%	-55%	-77%	65	13	5.5	2046	
EU27	-51%	-35%	-52%	-68%	40	14	3.0	2050	
India	287%	-9%	-36%	-63%	46	18	2.7	2047	
Russia	-45%	-28%	-58%	-89%	24	13	2.2	2042	
Japan	-37%	-35%	-53%	-71%	15	13	1.2	2048	
Nigeria	53%	-9%	-20%	-31%	4	29	0.1	2072	

Tab. 12: Linear emission paths - reference values big six – B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Using the framework data from Tab. 12 and comparing the results with the countries' commitments leads to the following results (see Tab. 13):

country	framework data Tab. 12	NDC (see Tab. 5)	deviation % points
China	-26%	+11%	-37%
United States	-33%	-41%	8%
EU27	-35%	-41%	6%
India	-9%	+18%	-26%
Russia	-28%	-8%	-20%
Japan	-35%	-36%	1%

Tab. 13: Comparison with NDCs (change 2030 vs. 2019) - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Disregarding the fact that the countries' targets generally refer to all greenhouse gases, the framework data used for Tab. 12 are a good representation of the current targets of the EU, USA and Japan for 2030.

The resulting national budgets based on the framework data in Tab. 12 also correspond to the implicit CO₂ budgets for these countries based on their NDCs (see Tab. 14):

Gt	national budget (Tab. 12)	implicit budget ³⁵ (Tab. 6)	deviation in %
China	160	332	108%
United States	65	73	12%
EU27	40	42	4%
India	46	91	98%
Russia	24	45	89%
Japan	15	17	13%
sum	350	600	71%

Tab. 14: Comparison with NDCs (budgets) - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

However, the results for China, India and Russia are far apart. Even India and Nigeria, would have to reduce their emissions significantly by 2030, despite far below-average per capita emissions in 2019 (see Tab. 2).³⁶

The question arises as to whether, for example, China and India could achieve the targets for 2030 according to Tab. 12 by taking a different emissions pathway. The framework data from Tab. 12 is used below to show the entire range of plausible emission paths (see Tab. 15):³⁷

China					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions		-2%
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt		0
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	-1%	12%	12%	12%	5%
2030	-44%	-26%	-18%	-5%	-26%
2035	-68%	-68%	-68%	-74%	-57%
2040	-82%	-89%	-94%	-102%	-88%
2045	-90%	-97%	-102%	-102%	-102%
2050	-94%	-102%	-102%	-102%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2061	2048	2044	2039	2042
overshoot in Gt	9.1	12.1	13.3	14.6	13.8
start change rate 2025	-10.8%	0.8%	0.8%	0.8%	-5.6%
national budget in Gt	160				

Tab. 15: RM Scenario Types - reference values China - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0³⁸

In scenario type RM-4, China would only have to reduce its emissions by 5% by 2030 compared to 2019. However, this has the price that emission neutrality must then be achieved earlier and more

³⁵ See Footnote 23 for the limitations.

³⁶ Our web application can also be used to assess whether a country's current trajectory is consistent with the assumed framework: <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info>.

³⁷ In scenario types RM 3 - 5, the rate of change for the starting year (here: 2025) can be specified on the basis of a realistic estimate. Since this rate of change is the basis for the entire trajectory of the following rates of change, a normalised value must be used that is not influenced by temporary effects such as the pandemic. For the reference values shown here, the actual rates for 2024 were used as the starting rate of change in scenario types RM 3 - 5. In order to find a solution in the respective scenario type, this starting value may have been adjusted slightly.

³⁸ Structure of the tables for the RM Scenario Types: The emission targets of scenario types RM 3 - 5 for 2030 are decrease in ambition from left to right.

net negative emissions must be realised. But even this scenario type is still far from China's 2030 target in its NDC (see Tab. 13).

Fig. 4: RM Scenario Types – emission paths and annual change rates China – B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0³⁹

The results for the scenario types are also shown below for the other countries analysed:

United States					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions	-2%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	0	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	-15%	-6%	-6%	-7%	-11%
2030	-48%	-32%	-25%	-15%	-33%
2035	-68%	-63%	-60%	-57%	-55%
2040	-80%	-83%	-86%	-94%	-77%
2045	-88%	-94%	-97%	-102%	-99%
2050	-92%	-98%	-102%	-102%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2066	2053	2048	2043	2046
overshoot in Gt	3.2	4.7	5.2	5.8	5.5
start change rate 2025	-9.2%	0.3%	0.3%	0.3%	-4.7%
national budget in Gt	65				

Tab. 16: RM Scenario Types - reference values USA - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

³⁹ Actual change rates shown in these figures: 2019 - 2024.

EU27					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions	-2%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	0	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	-22%	-17%	-17%	-17%	-19%
2030	-48%	-37%	-32%	-28%	-35%
2035	-65%	-59%	-54%	-47%	-52%
2040	-77%	-75%	-74%	-74%	-68%
2045	-84%	-86%	-88%	-93%	-85%
2050	-89%	-93%	-96%	-102%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2073	2062	2056	2050	2050
overshoot in Gt	1.4	2.2	2.5	3.0	3.0
start change rate 2025	-7.7%	-2.0%	-2.0%	-2.0%	-3.9%
national budget in Gt	40				

Tab. 17: RM Scenario Types - reference values EU - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Fig. 5: RM Scenario Types – emission paths and annual change rates EU – B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

India					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions	-2%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	0	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	13%	29%	29%	29%	18%
2030	-28%	3%	17%	36%	-9%
2035	-54%	-45%	-42%	-45%	-36%
2040	-70%	-78%	-85%	-98%	-63%
2045	-81%	-93%	-99%	-102%	-90%
2050	-88%	-99%	-102%	-102%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2072	2052	2046	2041	2047
overshoot in Gt	1.3	2.5	2.8	3.0	2.7
start change rate 2025	-8.6%	4.6%	4.6%	4.6%	-4.4%
national budget in Gt	46				

Tab. 18: RM Scenario Types - reference values India - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

The target value in scenario type RM-3 for 2030 could be compatible with India's NDC (cf. Tab. 4 and Tab. 13). But in this scenario type and with the assumptions made here about the global framework data, India would have to achieve emission neutrality as early as 2046 instead of 2070 as set out in its NDC.

Russia					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions		-2%
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt		0
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	-4%	11%	11%	11%	2%
2030	-45%	-26%	-16%	-1%	-28%
2035	-69%	-70%	-72%	-82%	-58%
2040	-83%	-91%	-96%	-102%	-89%
2045	-90%	-98%	-102%	-102%	-102%
2050	-94%	-102%	-102%	-102%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2061	2047	2043	2038	2042
overshoot in Gt	1.4	2.0	2.1	2.3	2.2
start change rate 2025	-10.8%	2.9%	3.0%	3.0%	-5.6%
national budget in Gt	24				

Tab. 19: RM Scenario Types - reference values Russia - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Japan					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions		-2%
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt		0
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	-21%	-16%	-16%	-16%	-17%
2030	-48%	-39%	-35%	-30%	-35%
2035	-66%	-61%	-57%	-51%	-53%
2040	-78%	-77%	-77%	-76%	-71%
2045	-86%	-88%	-89%	-93%	-89%
2050	-91%	-94%	-96%	-101%	-102%
year emissions neutrality	2071	2061	2056	2050	2048
overshoot in Gt	0.6	0.9	1.0	1.1	1.2
start change rate 2025	-8.2%	-3.0%	-3.0%	-3.0%	-4.2%
national budget in Gt	15				

Tab. 20: RM Scenario Types - reference values Japan - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Nigeria					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	550		minimum emissions	-2%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	0	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	1%	10%	10%	10%	2%
2030	-18%	13%	24%	34%	-9%
2035	-32%	-2%	15%	38%	-20%
2040	-45%	-24%	-12%	2%	-31%
2045	-55%	-46%	-46%	-56%	-42%
2050	-63%	-65%	-73%	-92%	-53%
year emissions neutrality	2097	2076	2064	2054	2072
overshoot in Gt	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.1	0.1
start change rate 2025	-3.9%	4.8%	4.8%	4.8%	-2.1%
national budget in Gt	4				

Tab. 21: RM Scenario Types - reference values Nigeria - B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Fig. 6: RM Scenario Types – emission paths and annual change rates Nigeria – B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

Fig. 7: Emission paths major emitters (RM-3-lin) – B550 / P15 / NNE2 / LUC0

4.3 Exemplary global framework data reflect the NDCs of China and India

This deliberately explores a counterfactual upper-risk envelope to illustrate what would be required to approximate the NDCs of China and India.

In order to obtain targets for China and India that move in the direction of their NDCs, the global budget, the LUC budget and the potential for net negative emissions would each have to be changed in a direction and to an extent that would significantly increase the risk of not successfully limiting global warming (see Tab. 22 and Tab. 23). In particular, the risks of such a massive negative LUC budget and such a high potential for net negative emissions are hardly acceptable.⁴⁰

On the other hand, there would then be a scope for the EU and Japan to provide budgets to India and China. For example, with the framework data from Tab. 12, the EU would receive a budget of around 40 Gt; in Tab. 24 it would be around 61 Gt. However, due to the small share of the EU and Japan in global emissions, the resulting scope is small.

⁴⁰ See Footnote 9 and (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025e).

China					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	650		minimum emissions	-25%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	-180	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	7%	12%	12%	12%	8%
2030	-13%	4%	10%	15%	-5%
2035	-29%	-12%	-1%	12%	-18%
2040	-42%	-30%	-19%	-4%	-31%
2045	-52%	-47%	-40%	-30%	-45%
2050	-62%	-62%	-60%	-60%	-58%
year emissions neutrality	2071	2065	2062	2058	2066
overshoot in Gt	69.7	91.0	105.1	121.0	88.1
start change rate 2025	-4.0%	0.8%	0.8%	0.8%	-2.4%
national budget in Gt	244				

Tab. 22: RM Scenario Types - reference values China – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

Fig. 8: RM Scenario Types – emission paths and annual change rates China – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

India					
global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	650		minimum emissions	-25%	
weighting population	15%		LUC budget in Gt	-180	
scenario type:	RM-1-const	RM-5-rad	RM-3-lin	RM-4-quadr	RM-6-abs
target year	changes versus 2019				
2025	19%	29%	29%	29%	21%
2030	-1%	34%	47%	57%	8%
2035	-18%	20%	43%	70%	-6%
2040	-32%	-4%	17%	45%	-19%
2045	-44%	-29%	-20%	-15%	-32%
2050	-53%	-51%	-54%	-71%	-46%
year emissions neutrality	2077	2065	2059	2054	2071
overshoot in Gt	11.0	20.6	25.2	29.3	16.2
start change rate 2025	-3.7%	4.5%	4.6%	4.5%	-2.2%
national budget in Gt	69				

Tab. 23: RM Scenario Types - reference values India – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

Fig. 9: RM Scenario Types – emission paths and annual change rates India – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

global CO2 budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt				650	minimum annual emissions			-25%
weighting population				15%	LUC budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt			-180
reference values (linear emission paths. RM-6)					budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt	scope years	temporary overshoot in Gt	year emissions neutrality
target year:	2030	2030	2035	2040				
reference year:	1990	2019						
China	366%	-5%	-18%	-31%	244	21	88.1	2066
United States	-19%	-19%	-29%	-39%	98	20	29.8	2071
EU27	-43%	-25%	-34%	-42%	61	21	13.1	2075
India	357%	8%	-6%	-19%	69	27	16.2	2071
Russia	-29%	-7%	-20%	-33%	37	20	13.7	2067
Japan	-27%	-24%	-33%	-42%	23	21	5.6	2074
Nigeria	62%	-4%	-11%	-18%	6	44	0.0	-

Tab. 24: Linear emission paths - reference values big six – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

Gt	national budget (Tab. 24)	implicit budget ⁴¹ (Tab. 6)	devia- tion in %
China	244	332	36%
United States	98	73	-26%
EU27	61	42	-32%
India	69	91	32%
Russia	37	45	23%
Japan	23	17	-26%
sum	532	600	13%

Tab. 25: Comparison with NDCs (budgets) – B650 / P15 / NNE25 / LUC180

⁴¹ See Footnote 23 for the limitations.

5 Conclusions

In the context of the Paris Ambition (Ratchet) Mechanism, the ESPM is designed to serve a dual purpose: to **support political decision-making** by mapping feasible option spaces under scientific constraints, and to provide transparent **reference values** against which existing NDCs can be assessed. The following elements enable these functions:

- The ESPM approach explicitly leaves open how a national CO₂ budget is determined. The weighted distribution key used here for a global CO₂ budget with the two components "emissions share" and "population share" in a base year represents a pragmatic approach that can map the two most important factors "current reality" and "equity" (see Excursus 3).
- With the RM Scenario Types offered in the ESPM (see Excursus 5), national paths can be derived that adhere to a predefined budget and take socio-economic factors into account. The scenario types ultimately enable a transparent political decision on emission paths.

The emission targets for the world's six major emitters presented here are only examples, as important framework data need to be decided politically.⁴² This results in the following political agenda for each Party to the Paris Agreement:⁴³

Political agenda:

1. Concretise **global framework data** based on the state of scientific knowledge, especially with regard to the global CO₂ budget and the scope of net negative emissions.
2. Derive a **national CO₂ budget** on this base that ensure a fair and economically sensible distribution of a global CO₂ budget.⁴⁴
3. When setting **emission targets**, choose an emission path that makes sense in terms of overall policy. This is best achieved by setting **sensible annual rates of change**.⁴⁵
4. **Adjust** the framework data and reduction targets regularly on the basis of new scientific findings and technical/real developments.

⁴² This web app can be used to specify a variety of global framework data: <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info>.

⁴³ At present, a corresponding global agreement does not appear realistic. Therefore, in the sense of the bottom-up approach of the Paris Ratchet Mechanism, each country is to address the elements of the following agenda for itself. However, this can initiate a global discourse that contributes to Paris-compatible NDCs in aggregate. In addition, the major emitters need to find a binding negotiation format (cf. Edenhofer, 2022). The failure of the Copenhagen negotiations in 2009 under a top-down approach does not preclude asking today what constitutes a fair, realistic and economically sensible national contribution to global mitigation efforts.

⁴⁴ See Excursus 3: Allocation of a global CO₂ budget.

⁴⁵ See Excursus 5: Regensburg Model Scenario Types.

Despite the exemplary nature of the results shown here, they provide important indications of which scenarios / framework data lead to realistic national emission targets that sum up to a Paris-compatible global emissions budget.

An important finding is that there is a fundamental trade-off between nationally achievable emission pathways consistent with the 1.5 °C limit and commonly applied notions of climate justice.

The following is now crucial:⁴⁶

- We have to face the difficult task of identifying achievable national targets that are consistent with the Paris Agreement and adequately address climate justice. In doing so, concessions will be necessary, both in terms of orientation towards the 1.5 °C limit and in terms of the per capita distribution of a remaining global CO₂ budget.
- Major emitters should find a negotiating format to agree on Paris-compatible and binding targets. The UN climate conferences are not the appropriate format for such negotiations because of the unanimity rule of over 190 countries (cf. Edenhofer, 2022).
- The figures show that an urgent solution is needed to address the structural incompatibility between China's emissions pathway and Paris-compatible global CO₂ budget constraints (cf. for example: Tab. 6, Tab. 13 and Fig. 2). This mitigation gap is particularly critical for achieving the Paris climate targets, firstly because of China's high share of global emissions and secondly because the rapid reduction in emissions that is actually necessary may not seem feasible.
- But the emissions of emerging nations such as India must also fall soon. If emissions continue to rise in these countries, as they have in recent years, then the Paris climate targets will also not be achievable. The decarbonisation of the Global South must be financially supported. On its path to greater prosperity, the Global South must leapfrog the high-carbon era of the old industrialised countries.
- However, all parties to the Paris Agreement are required to submit NDCs that reflect the global reduction needs as set out in the Global Stocktake ([GST](#)). Overall, the NDCs are still far from being compatible with the Paris Agreement.⁴⁷
- Paris-compatible NDCs are the first step. The second, equally important step is to ensure that these targets are actually met. Hard emission caps in emissions trading systems could ensure this, for example (cf. Expertenrat für Klimafragen, 2022, p. 17). As long as there are

⁴⁶ [This](#) paper aims to identify global framework data that can lead to achievable national targets: (Wolfsteiner, 2026).

⁴⁷ Cf. (UNFCCC, 2023; UNFCCC, 2024; UNEP, 2024; UNFCCC, 2025).

no collectively Paris-compatible NDCs — and no credible assurance that they will be met — additional forms of cooperation will be required to create a level playing field for companies. The room for manoeuvre of individual countries is otherwise constrained by the risk of carbon leakage whenever corporate-level climate action entails higher costs.

- Under robust institutional conditions, market-based cooperation under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement could complement Paris-compatible NDCs by improving cost efficiency and supporting international burden-sharing.⁴⁸

⁴⁸ See Excursus 4: Implications of the mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement.

Tools and further exemplary results

For the calculation of the exemplary results in this paper we have used the Excel tool "ESPM" (version 79.0), which can be downloaded from the [zenodo](#) platform (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025b).

Further exemplary results for the six largest emitters with different framework data and RM Scenario Types are shown at <https://espm.save-the-climate.info/>.

The web app <https://national-budgets.climate-calculator.info/> can be used to calculate Paris-compatible CO₂ budgets for all countries in the world excluding LUC and ISA. This web app also shows the emission targets for a linear emission path. This allows the results shown here to be reproducible. Minor deviations may occur due to a different mathematical approach (cf. Wittmann & Wolfsteiner, 2023). The web app <https://GCP.national-budgets.climate-calculator.info> shows the corresponding results, including LUC. A more detailed [Excel tool](#) displays the results based on different data sources: (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025d).

The web app <https://paths.climate-calculator.info/> can be used to calculate emission paths that comply with a predefined CO₂ budget (corresponding [detailed Excel tool](#): (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2025a). In addition to linear emission paths, other scenario types are offered there (see Excursus 5: Regensburg Model Scenario Types).

The web app <https://IB-IWP.climate-calculator.info> can be used to calculate implicit emission budgets derived from an NDC and to calculate the implicit weighting of the population (see Chapter 2.1.3 NDC indicator: Implicit weighting of the population (IWP)).

At <https://climate-calculator.info> we provide an overview of the tools we offer.

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German Federal Constitutional Court on CO2 budgets

Excerpt from the main considerations of the Federal Constitutional Court (BVerfG, 2021):

“The constitutionally relevant temperature threshold of well below 2 °C and preferably 1.5 °C can in principle be converted into a global CO2 residual budget, which can then be distributed among the states. The Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) has named concrete global CO2 residual budgets for various temperature thresholds and various probabilities of occurrence on the basis of a quality-assurance procedure, disclosing the remaining uncertainty. On this basis, the German Advisory Council on the Environment [(SRU, 2020)], note by the authors] has also determined a concrete national residual budget for Germany from 2020 that would be compatible with the Paris target. Due to the uncertainties and evaluations contained therein, the budget size determined cannot currently provide a numerically accurate measure for constitutional court review. The legislature still has room for manoeuvre. However, it may not fill this space at its political discretion. If there is scientific uncertainty about environmentally relevant causal relationships, Article 20a of the Basic Law imposes a special duty of care on the legislature. According to this, already reliable indications of the possibility of serious or irreversible impairments must be taken into account. At present, a violation of this duty of care cannot be established. It follows that estimates by the IPCC on the size of the remaining global CO2 residual budget must be taken into account, even though they contain uncertainties. The emission levels regulated in Article 4 para. 1 sentence 3 KSG [Climate Protection Act, note by the authors] in conjunction with Annex 2 would largely exhaust the residual budget determined by the German Advisory Council on the Environment on the basis of the IPCC estimates until the year 2030. However, compared to the uncertainties currently included in the calculation of the residual budget, the degree of shortfall did not form a sufficient basis for a constitutional court challenge.”

Excursus 1: German Federal Constitutional Court on CO2 budgets

German Federal Constitutional Court on freedom opportunities for future generations

Excerpt from the guiding principles of the decision of the Federal Constitutional Court (BVerfG, 2021):

“Under certain conditions, the Basic Law obliges the safeguarding of freedom protected by fundamental rights over time and the proportionate distribution of opportunities for freedom over the generations. In terms of subjective law, fundamental rights, as an intertemporal safeguard of freedom, protect against a unilateral shifting of the greenhouse gas reduction burden imposed by Article 20a GG [Basic Law, note by the authors] to the future. The objective-law protection mandate of Article 20a of the Basic Law also includes the necessity to treat the natural foundations of life with such care and to leave them to posterity in such a condition that future generations could not continue to preserve them only at the price of radical abstinence of their own. The protection of future freedom also requires that the transition to climate neutrality be initiated in good time. In concrete terms, this requires the early formulation of transparent targets for further greenhouse gas reductions that provide orientation for the necessary development and implementation processes and give them a sufficient degree of development pressure and planning certainty.”

Excursus 2: German Federal Constitutional Court on freedom opportunities for future generations

Allocation of a global CO₂ budget

The global community has set itself the following framework:

“Acknowledging that the global nature of climate change calls for the widest possible cooperation by all countries and their participation in an effective and appropriate international response, in accordance with their common but differentiated responsibilities and respective capabilities and their social and economic conditions.”

United Nations Climate Change Framework Convention of 1992

Five basic allocation approaches can be distinguished:⁴⁹

- (1) Grandfathering
- (2) Equality
- (3) Responsibility
- (4) Capability
- (5) Cost efficiency

Fig. 10: Allocation principles for the distribution of a remaining global CO₂ budget⁵⁰

⁴⁹ See (Dekker, et al., 2025) for a comprehensive classification of effort-sharing approaches and an assessment of their influence on national targets under different equity, strategic, and scientific assumptions. See also (Robiou du Pont, et al., 2017, p. 40; Robiou du Pont, et al., 2025).

⁵⁰ “Allocation and fairness principles (corners of the pentagon, in black) and methods to quantify these principles or combinations thereof (in coloured or grey text boxes)” (Dekker, et al., 2025, Supplementary information). Source of the figure: (Dekker, et al., 2025, Supplementary information: Figure SI.3). Original figure concept based on (Höhne, et al., 2014).

In the field labelled ‘Per capita convergence’, ‘**or Weighting**’ has been added to reflect the approach used in this paper.

In addition to the allocation keys "current emissions share" (1) and "current population share" (2) used here, other criteria may therefore be taken into account such as historical emissions (3) or GDP per capita (4).

Including historical emissions highlights the responsibility of the "old" industrialised countries for the decarbonisation process, but results in unrealistic territorial emission targets. However, historical emissions could play a significant role, especially in compensating for [Loss and Damage](#).

The idea behind "capability" is that wealthier countries should set themselves more ambitious goals. Since there is a correlation between emissions per capita and GDP per capita for the six largest emitters (cf. Tab. 26), the GDP per capita criterion is already indirectly mapped via the weighting of the population. However, the correlation coefficient of 0.7 is clearly below 1, so that this mapping is not perfect. In principle, it might make more sense to use criteria based on economic performance for direct financial issues such as contributions to [Climate Finance](#).

correlation	per capita	
	emissions in t	GDP in TUSD
India	2	7
EU27	7	45
China	8	16
Japan	9	41
Russia	13	28
United States	15	62
correlation coefficient	0.68	

Tab. 26: GDP per capita of the six largest emitters

Instead of allocating a global budget, a global path can be allocated by using a convergence model [also a combination of the approaches (1) and (2)] (cf. Sargl, et al., 2024a). Using a convergence model implies an implicit weighting of the population that is the same for all countries (cf. Wittmann & Wolfsteiner, 2023). In the Regensburg Model convergence approach, this implicit weighting is around 12% with a linear emission path and a per capita emissions convergence at 0.5 t (cf. Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2024b; Sargl, et al., 2024b). Due to its characteristics, the Regensburg Model can be described as a kind of "moral floor" for the industrialised countries.

Another approach (5) are Integrated Assessment Models (IAMs), which can be used to identify globally cost-efficient national emission paths (cf. van Soest, et al., 2021).⁵¹ But the results of IAMs are a "black box" for policy makers. For the ESPM approach, on the other hand, only a few framework data need to be specified politically and equity aspects can be explicitly considered. This means that emissions paths can ultimately be determined politically in a transparent manner in the ESPM, taking socio-economic factors into account.

In convergence models and IAMs, the national budgets and thus the distribution of a global CO₂ budget result indirectly.

A distinction can be made whether the allocation of a global CO₂ budget refers to the actual territorial emissions of a country or to tradable emission rights.⁵²

If allocation is based on emission rights, the scope for climate justice can be considered even greater (Rajamani, et al., 2021; Robiou du Pont, et al., 2025). However, it is important to keep in mind that the resulting potential financial flows in a subsequent emissions trading should be realistic.

⁵¹ For a recent approach that derives nationally consistent emission targets from global welfare-optimizing IAM scenarios, see (van der Wijst, et al., 2025).

⁵² See also Excursus 4: Implications of the mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement.

If the allocation is based on territorial emissions, it would have to be examined whether it makes sense for countries with low per capita emissions today to build up an economy that is more fossil fuel-based and has to decarbonise again soon afterwards.

When allocating a global CO2 budget, it should be taken into account that it must also work for countries with currently high per capita emissions or high per capita GDP.

Two aspects should be considered here:

Territorial emission targets or payments within the framework of global emission trading

- (1) must also be politically enforceable at national level.
- (2) should also be economically viable in the sense that the global economy is not unduly affected. This would otherwise also have a considerable negative impact on countries with low per capita GDP.

An ethical justification for these aspects can be found in **Rawls' "Theory of Justice"**.

Excursus 3: Allocation of a global CO2 budget

Implications of the mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement

Do market- and cooperation-based mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement solve the problem of a scarce global CO2 budget?

The market- and cooperation-based mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement (hereinafter: *Article 6 mechanisms*) cannot resolve scarcity; it can, at most, improve **cost efficiency under a given aggregate ambition level** and — depending on the implicit population weighting embedded in current NDCs — may trigger financial flows that can contribute to financial burden-sharing between countries that is perceived as more **equitable**.

Furthermore, Article 6 mechanisms cannot meaningfully compensate for extreme global framework assumptions, such as a high weighting of population in the allocation of a global CO2 budget, which would imply large and politically unrealistic international financial flows (see Excursus 3: Allocation of a global CO2 budget).

In a worst-case scenario, however, Article 6 mechanisms may lead to the large-scale generation of so-called “hot air”, i.e. nominal emission reductions without additional global climate impact. ‘Hot air’ here is used as an umbrella term for transfers that are nominally valid under accounting rules but lack real global mitigation impact, whether due to non-compliance, weak baselines or non-additional outcomes.

What works well in these mechanisms — and where do the risks lie?

A clear advantage of the mechanisms under Article 6 is the avoidance of double counting. Countries that sell emission reductions (internationally transferred mitigation outcomes, ITMOs) must add these amounts to their accounted national emissions (i.e. the emissions counted for NDC compliance, which are based on territorial emissions but adjusted through corresponding adjustments under Article 6), while purchasing countries may subtract them. As a result, the same emissions cannot be counted more than once in principle.

If all Parties complied with their NDCs and if these NDCs were Paris-compatible in aggregate, Article 6 mechanisms could indeed contribute to higher cost efficiency and outcomes that may be perceived as more equitable.

But there is a significant incentive to sell ITMOs and subsequently fail to meet one’s own NDC, since non-compliance with an NDC is not subject to sanctions beyond public scrutiny (“naming and shaming”). This represents a central risk, as even formally robust accounting through corresponding adjustments does not prevent a real increase in global emissions if Parties do not actually comply with their NDCs. The Article-6 rulebook seeks to mitigate this risk through authorisation, accounting (corresponding adjustments) and reporting requirements intended to ensure that transfers do not undermine achievement of the NDC; however, robust ex ante verification remains systemically difficult.

If the NDCs are not Paris-compatible overall, the question arises as to whether the Article 6 mechanisms can help to raise the level of ambition globally beyond that implied by existing NDCs.

In principle, international transfers under Article 6 may enable additional mitigation efforts by mobilising financial resources and lowering domestic mitigation costs. However, under the accounting logic of the Paris Agreement, such transfers merely reallocate emission reductions between countries and do not reduce global emissions per se. Genuine global additionality would only arise if the purchasing country either tightened its NDC beyond the use of transferred units or cancelled part of the acquired mitigation outcomes. Without such buyer-side action, international transfers substitute for, rather than add to, domestic mitigation.

Narrative description (“thought experiment”) for clarification:

Assuming that both Parties ultimately comply with their NDCs, transfers under Article 6 can shift mitigation efforts across countries but do not, by themselves, lower global emissions below the aggregate level implied by those NDCs.

Consider a country that recognises it could follow a more ambitious CO₂ emissions pathway than implied by its current NDC if additional financial resources were available. Article 6 mechanisms can provide such resources by allowing the country to sell mitigation outcomes to another country. As a result, additional emission reductions may indeed be realised in the selling country.

However, if the purchasing country uses the acquired mitigation outcomes solely to comply with its existing NDC, no additional global emission reduction occurs. In this case, the additional reductions in the selling country merely replace mitigation efforts that the purchasing country would otherwise have had to undertake domestically in order to meet its own NDC.

Global additionality would only arise if the purchasing country exceeded its existing NDC, for example by cancelling part of the acquired mitigation outcomes or by tightening its target accordingly. In the absence of such action by the purchasing country, Article 6 transfers re-distribute mitigation efforts across countries but do not reduce global emissions beyond the aggregate level implied by existing NDCs.

What would be the optimal solution?

From an analytical perspective, an optimal structure would be a global emissions trading system based on binding top-down national CO₂ budgets or a hard global cap. At present, neither option is politically feasible.

A step in the right direction would be to require that the national CO₂ budget claimed by an NDC be made explicit. Today, the implicit CO₂ budget underlying an NDC can often only be roughly estimated. See, for examples, this web application: <https://ib-iwp.climate-calculator.info> and (cf. Wolfsteiner, 2025a). Making it explicit would facilitate a global comparison of ambition levels and significantly improve the assessment of whether NDCs are Paris-compatible in aggregate. To initiate such a process, some countries could take the lead voluntarily.

What can be expected under the current Article 6 mechanisms?

At present, countries primarily act in line with their own interests, seeking to maximise their national CO₂ budgets and to optimise revenues or minimise compliance costs within the framework of Article 6 mechanisms.

- **Emerging and developing countries** often favour a high (implicit) population weighting, which makes compliance easier and thereby contributes to the generation of surplus mitigation outcomes for export.
- **Industrialized countries and China**, by contrast, tend to favour a low population weighting or a high weighting of base-year emissions, which increases their own entitlement budgets and reduces the need to import mitigation outcomes.

These strategies are not mutually compatible. The result is a **structural imbalance**: many potential exporters, but limited demand. This imbalance is reinforced by the fact that surplus units are often generated under **conservatively ambitious NDCs**, raising concerns about **questionable additionality** and the risk of “hot air.” Such a market could divert capital from transformative mitigation and undermine the environmental integrity of Article 6.

Conclusion

A key prerequisite for preventing “hot air” and realising the potential benefits of the Article 6 mechanisms would be NDCs that are Paris-compatible in aggregate, combined with institutional frameworks that credibly ensure compliance.

This requires

- (1) a global discourse on appropriate and achievable national Paris-compatible CO2 budgets – what is a normative objective of the ESPM applied here,⁵³ and
- (2) instruments that credibly ensure compliance with national climate targets — most importantly emissions trading systems with a hard emissions cap.

Excursus 4: Implications of the mechanisms under Article 6 of the Paris Agreement

⁵³ Assuming converging underlying global framework data, Tab. 27 illustrates the theoretical scope for budget transfers within the ESPM framework. Countries with a comparatively large scope (shown there as the national CO2 budget divided by emissions in 2019) tend to exhibit greater model-based leeway for potential transfers. However, this does not imply automatic transferability under Article 6, as this depends on the actual over-fulfilment of the NDC and the corresponding adjustments.

Regensburg Model Scenario Types

From an overall perspective of climate policy, scenarios with a nonlinear emissions path may be useful. Additional scenario types also offer the possibility of taking country-specific features into account.

The Regensburg Model Scenario Types RM 1 - 5 are based on the course of the annual change rates. Annual rates of change are used in many areas and are particularly suitable for describing a meaningful course of emission paths.

Four basic types can be distinguished in a monotonically decreasing progression of the annual rates of change:

- (1) Constant: constant annual reduction rates (RM-1, straight line)
- (2) Linear: linearly monotonically decreasing (RM-3; straight line)
- (3) Concave: initially under-proportional monotonically decreasing (RM-2, RM-4)
- (4) Convex: initially over-proportional monotonically decreasing (RM-5)

In addition, the scenario type RM-6 uses linear emission paths. Accordingly, the annual reduction rates for RM-6 have a concave course and the annual reduction amount is constant.

With our **web app** <https://paths.climate-calculator.info/> the different scenario types can be graphically traced (see also Fig. 1 and e.g. Fig. 4).

For a comprehensive mathematical description, we [refer to](#): (Wolfsteiner & Wittmann, 2024a).

The advantage of scenario types RM 3 - 5 is that the start change rate can be specified on the basis of the real circumstances and that increasing emissions can also be mapped by specifying a positive start change rate.

The following questions should be considered, when assessing a scenario type:

- (1) Which annual change rates are when realistic?
- (2) Does an initially slowly rising level of ambition (RM-2/4 and RM-6) imply an unjustifiable burden for the future, since this later implies very high reduction rates?
- (3) Do high later reduction rates make sense, if they provide a longer lead time for the necessary investments and the investments could then rather be made within the framework of normal investment cycles? However, this requires a very credible climate policy backed by effective instruments.
- (4) Does an initially rapidly rising level of ambition (RM-3 and RM-5) convey a more credible climate protection policy that creates planning security for public and private investments in a fossil-free future?

The German Advisory Council on the Environment (SRU) recommends to refrain from linear emission paths (RM-6): "*A slow start, hoping for steep emission reductions in later years, jeopardises compliance with the budget and climate targets*" (SRU, 2020, p. 56). This argument would also apply to the scenario types RM-2 and RM-4.

The decision of the German Federal Constitutional Court on the Climate Protection Act also implicitly poses the question of what annual change rates we must accept today so that the freedom of future generations is not unduly restricted (see Excursus 2: German Federal Constitutional Court on freedom opportunities for future generations).

To avoid very high annual reduction rates in later years, the scenario types RM-3 and RM-5 are suitable.

References

BVerfG, 2021. *Beschluss des Ersten Senats vom 24. März 2021- 1 BvR 2656/18 -, Rn. 1-270.*

[Online]

Available at: http://www.bverfg.de/e/rs20210324_1bvr265618.html

Dekker, M. M. et al., 2025. Navigating the black box of fair national emissions targets. *Nat. Clim. Chang.*, 16 06, Volume 15, pp. 752 - 759.

Edenhofer, O., 2022. *COP27: Climate expert Edenhofer dampens expectations; we need new negotiating formats (Interview).* [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7419448>

EDGAR, 2025. *European Commission, Joint Research Centre (JRC)/PBL Netherlands Environmental Assessment Agency. Emission Database for Global Atmospheric Research (EDGAR).* [Online]

Available at: <https://edgar.jrc.ec.europa.eu/>

[Accessed 09 09 2025].

Expertenrat für Klimafragen, 2022. *Zweijahresgutachten 2022 - Gutachten zur Entwicklung der Treibhausgasemissionen, Trends der Jahresemissionsmengen und zur Wirksamkeit von Maßnahmen.* [Online]

Available at: <https://www.expertenrat-klima.de/publikationen/>

GCP, 2025. [Online]

Available at: <https://globalcarbonbudget.org>

[Accessed 13 11 2025].

Höhne, N., den Elzen, M. & Escalante, D., 2014. Regional GHG reduction targets based on effort sharing: a comparison of studies. *Climate Policy*, Volume 14, pp. 122 - 147.

IPCC, 2019. *Special Report on Climate Change and Land (SRCCL).* [Online]

Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/srccl>

IPCC, 2021. *Climate Change 2021: The Physical Science Basis. Contribution of Working Group I to the Sixth Assessment Report of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change.* [Online]

Available at: <https://www.ipcc.ch/report/ar6/wg1/>

Rajamani, L. et al., 2021. National 'fair shares' in reducing greenhouse gas emissions within the principled framework of international environmental law. *Climate Policy*.

Raupach, M. R. et al., 2014. Sharing a quota on cumulative carbon emissions. *Nature Climate Change*, Volume 4, pp. 873 - 879.

Robiou du Pont, Y., Dekker, M., van Vuuren, D. & Schaefer, M., 2025. Effect of discontinuous fair-share emissions allocations immediately based on equity. *Nat Commun*, Issue 16.

Robiou du Pont, Y. et al., 2017. Equitable mitigation to achieve the Paris Agreement goals. *Nature Climate Change*, January, Volume 7, pp. 38 - 40.

Sargl, M., Wiegand, D., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2021. Berechnung Paris-kompatibler Emissionsziele für die sechs größten Emittenten mit dem ESPM. *Zeitschrift für Umweltpolitik & Umweltrecht*, Issue 3/2021, pp. 269 - 286.

Sargl, M., Wiegand, D., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2024a. *Distribution of a Global CO2 Budget - A Comparison of Resource Sharing Models*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4603032>

Sargl, M., Wiegand, D., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2025. *Berechnung Paris-kompatibler Emissionspfade mit dem ESPM am Beispiel Deutschlands und der EU*. [Online]
Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5678717>

Sargl, M., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2017. The Regensburg Model: reference values for the (I)NDCs based on converging per capita emissions. *Climate Policy*, 17(5), p. 664 – 677.

Sargl, M., Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2024b. *Calculation of Paris-compatible emission targets and CO2 budgets for the six largest emitters with the Regensburg Model*. [Online]
Available at: <https://zenodo.org/doi/10.5281/zenodo.6504452>

SRU, 2020. *Environmental Report 2020 - Chapter 2: Using the CO2 budget to meet the Paris climate targets*. [Online]
Available at: <https://www.umweltrat.de>

UNEP, 2024. *Emissions Gap Report 2024: No more hot air ... please! With a massive gap between rhetoric and reality, countries draft new climate commitments..* [Online]
Available at: <https://wedocs.unep.org/20.500.11822/46404>

UNFCCC, 2023. *Technical dialogue of the first global stocktake. Synthesis report by the co-facilitators on the technical dialogue*. [Online]
Available at: <https://unfccc.int/documents/631600>

UNFCCC, 2024. *NDC Synthesis Report*. [Online]
Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/nationally-determined-contributions-ndcs/2024-ndc-synthesis-report>

UNFCCC, 2025. *NDC Synthesis Report*. [Online]

Available at: <https://unfccc.int/process-and-meetings/the-paris-agreement/nationally-determined-contributions-ndcs/2025-ndc-synthesis-report>

van der Wijst, K.-I., Hof, A. & van Vuuren, D. P., 2025. Equity principles, mitigation and climate impacts: balancing welfare and costs. *Environmental Research Letters*.

van Soest, H. L., den Elzen, M. G. J. & van Vuuren, D. P., 2021. Net-zero emission targets for major emitting countries consistent with the Paris Agreement. *Nat Commun* 12.

Wiegand, D. et al., 2021. Berechnung Paris-kompatibler Emissionspfade mit dem ESP-Modell am Beispiel der EU. *Wirtschaftsdienst*, Februar, pp. 127 - 133.

Wittmann, G. & Wolfsteiner, A., 2023. *Resource Sharing Models – A Mathematical Description*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4405448>

Wolfsteiner, A., 2025a. *Ableitung eines impliziten CO₂-Budgets für Deutschland aus dem Klimaschutzgesetz*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6535174>

Wolfsteiner, A., 2025b. *Implicit weighting of the population in the allocation of a global CO₂ budget*. [Online]

Available at: <https://iwp.climate-calculator.info/>

Wolfsteiner, A., 2025c. *What does the IPCC say about the remaining CO₂ budgets?*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.16731850>

Wolfsteiner, A., 2026. *Global Framework Data for Achievable, Collectively Paris-compatible National CO₂ Targets*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17856181>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2024a. *Mathematical Description of the Regensburg Model Scenario Types RM 1 – 6*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4540475>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2024b. *Paris-compatible National CO₂ Budgets for the Six Major Emitters Based on the Regensburg Model with Converging Per Capita Emissions*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13969419>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025a. *Tool for the Calculation of Emission Paths with the RM Scenario Types*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4568839>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025b. *Tool for the Calculation of Paris-compatible Emission Paths with the ESPM*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4580310>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025c. *Tool for the Calculation of Paris-compatible Global Emission Paths with the RM Scenario Types*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4584562>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025d. *Tool: Implicit and explicit weighting of the population in the allocation of a global CO2 budget*. [Online]

Available at: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5837866>

Wolfsteiner, A. & Wittmann, G., 2025e. *Treatment of the topics LUC and net negative emissions in the RM and ESPM tools*. [Online]

Available at: <https://luc.climate-calculator.info>

Appendix: Exemplary national budgets with different global framework data

global budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt				550	LUC budget	0	global budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt				650	LUC budget	0	global budget 2020 - 2100 in Gt				650	LUC budget	0
weighting population				50%			weighting population				50%			weighting population				15%		
sorted by national budget	national budget 2020 - 2100	weighted key	emissions 2019	scope years			sorted by national budget	national budget 2020 - 2100	weighted key	emissions 2019	scope years			sorted by national budget	national budget 2020 - 2100	weighted key	emissions 2019	scope years		
	Gt	Gt	Gt					Gt	Gt	Gt					Gt	Gt	Gt			
China	134.6	25.3%	11.81	11			China	159.2	25.3%	11.81	13			China	189.5	30.1%	11.81	16		
India	65.7	12.4%	2.55	26			India	77.7	12.4%	2.55	30			United States	76.4	12.1%	4.97	15		
United States	47.4	8.9%	4.97	10			United States	56.0	8.9%	4.97	11			India	53.9	8.6%	2.55	21		
EU27	36.4	6.8%	2.91	13			EU27	43.0	6.8%	2.91	15			EU27	47.8	7.6%	2.91	16		
Russia	18.4	3.5%	1.86	10			Russia	21.8	3.5%	1.86	12			Russia	28.8	4.6%	1.86	16		
Indonesia	13.9	2.6%	0.64	22			Indonesia	16.5	2.6%	0.64	26			Japan	17.9	2.9%	1.12	16		
Japan	12.5	2.4%	1.12	11			Japan	14.8	2.4%	1.12	13			Indonesia	12.6	2.0%	0.64	20		
Brazil	10.7	2.0%	0.47	23			Brazil	12.7	2.0%	0.47	27			Iran	11.4	1.8%	0.71	16		
Pakistan	8.5	1.6%	0.20	43			Pakistan	10.0	1.6%	0.20	51			Germany	11.2	1.8%	0.70	16		
Mexico	8.1	1.5%	0.49	16			Mexico	9.6	1.5%	0.49	20			South Korea	10.2	1.6%	0.65	16		
Iran	8.0	1.5%	0.71	11			Iran	9.5	1.5%	0.71	13			Brazil	9.4	1.5%	0.47	20		
Germany	7.9	1.5%	0.70	11			Germany	9.3	1.5%	0.70	13			Canada	9.3	1.5%	0.61	15		
Nigeria	7.8	1.5%	0.13	62			Nigeria	9.3	1.5%	0.13	74			Saudi Arabia	8.9	1.4%	0.58	15		
Bangladesh	6.6	1.2%	0.11	60			Bangladesh	7.8	1.2%	0.11	71			Mexico	8.8	1.4%	0.49	18		
South Korea	6.5	1.2%	0.65	10			South Korea	7.7	1.2%	0.65	12			South Africa	7.7	1.2%	0.48	16		
Türkiye	5.9	1.1%	0.41	14			Türkiye	6.9	1.1%	0.41	17			Türkiye	7.1	1.1%	0.41	17		
Viet Nam	5.8	1.1%	0.34	17			Viet Nam	6.9	1.1%	0.34	20			Australia	6.3	1.0%	0.41	15		
Canada	5.7	1.1%	0.61	9			Canada	6.7	1.1%	0.61	11			Viet Nam	6.1	1.0%	0.34	18		
South Africa	5.5	1.0%	0.48	11			South Africa	6.5	1.0%	0.48	14			United Kingdom	6.1	1.0%	0.36	17		
Saudi Arabia	5.4	1.0%	0.58	9			Saudi Arabia	6.4	1.0%	0.58	11			Italy, San Marino and the	5.6	0.9%	0.33	17		
Egypt	5.2	1.0%	0.24	22			Egypt	6.2	1.0%	0.24	26			France and Monaco	5.5	0.9%	0.32	17		
United Kingdom	4.9	0.9%	0.36	14			United Kingdom	5.8	0.9%	0.36	16			Pakistan	5.4	0.9%	0.20	27		
Philippines	4.8	0.9%	0.15	32			Philippines	5.7	0.9%	0.15	38			Thailand	5.0	0.8%	0.29	18		
France and Monaco	4.6	0.9%	0.32	14			France and Monaco	5.4	0.9%	0.32	17			Poland	5.0	0.8%	0.31	16		
Thailand	4.5	0.8%	0.29	16			Thailand	5.3	0.8%	0.29	18			Egypt	4.7	0.7%	0.24	20		
Italy, S. Mar., Holy See	4.5	0.8%	0.33	13			Italy, S. Mar., Holy See	5.3	0.8%	0.33	16			Taiwan	4.5	0.7%	0.29	16		
Ethiopia	3.9	0.7%	0.02	213			Ethiopia	4.6	0.7%	0.02	252			Nigeria	4.3	0.7%	0.13	34		
Australia	3.8	0.7%	0.41	9			Australia	4.5	0.7%	0.41	11			Spain and Andorra	4.3	0.7%	0.25	17		
Poland	3.6	0.7%	0.31	11			Poland	4.2	0.7%	0.31	14			Malaysia	4.1	0.7%	0.26	16		
Spain and Andorra	3.4	0.6%	0.25	14			Spain and Andorra	4.1	0.6%	0.25	16			Bangladesh	3.6	0.6%	0.11	33		
Dem. Rep. of the Congo	3.0	0.6%	0.00	680			Dem. Rep. of the Congo	3.6	0.6%	0.00	804			Ukraine	3.6	0.6%	0.21	17		
Ukraine	3.0	0.6%	0.21	15			Ukraine	3.6	0.6%	0.21	17			Philippines	3.5	0.6%	0.15	24		
Malaysia	3.0	0.6%	0.26	12			Malaysia	3.5	0.6%	0.26	14			Kazakhstan	3.4	0.5%	0.22	16		
Taiwan	2.9	0.5%	0.29	10			Taiwan	3.5	0.5%	0.29	12			Iraq	3.3	0.5%	0.19	17		
Argentina	2.9	0.5%	0.18	16			Argentina	3.4	0.5%	0.18	19			Argentina	3.2	0.5%	0.18	18		
Iraq	2.8	0.5%	0.19	14			Iraq	3.3	0.5%	0.19	17			Algeria	3.2	0.5%	0.18	17		
Algeria	2.8	0.5%	0.18	15			Algeria	3.3	0.5%	0.18	18			United Arab Emirates	3.0	0.5%	0.20	15		
Colombia	2.3	0.4%	0.09	27			Colombia	2.8	0.4%	0.09	32			Netherlands	2.5	0.4%	0.16	16		
Kazakhstan	2.2	0.4%	0.22	10			Kazakhstan	2.6	0.4%	0.22	12			Venezuela	2.2	0.3%	0.12	18		
Tanzania	2.2	0.4%	0.02	131			Tanzania	2.6	0.4%	0.02	155			Uzbekistan	2.1	0.3%	0.12	18		
Myanmar/Burma	2.1	0.4%	0.03	62			Myanmar/Burma	2.5	0.4%	0.03	73			Colombia	1.9	0.3%	0.09	22		
Sudan and South Sudan	2.0	0.4%	0.02	87			Sudan and South Sudan	2.4	0.4%	0.02	103			Qatar	1.7	0.3%	0.12	15		
Venezuela	2.0	0.4%	0.12	17			Venezuela	2.4	0.4%	0.12	20			Czechia	1.6	0.3%	0.10	16		
Uzbekistan	2.0	0.4%	0.12	17			Uzbekistan	2.3	0.4%	0.12	20			Ethiopia	1.6	0.3%	0.02	87		
Kenya	1.9	0.4%	0.02	100			Kenya	2.3	0.4%	0.02	118			Chile	1.6	0.3%	0.10	17		
Morocco	1.8	0.3%	0.07	25			Morocco	2.1	0.3%	0.07	29			Belgium	1.6	0.3%	0.10	16		
United Arab Emirates	1.8	0.3%	0.20	9			United Arab Emirates	2.1	0.3%	0.20	11			Morocco	1.5	0.2%	0.07	21		
Netherlands	1.7	0.3%	0.16	11			Netherlands	2.1	0.3%	0.16	13			Kuwait	1.5	0.2%	0.10	15		
Uganda	1.6	0.3%	0.01	230			Uganda	1.9	0.3%	0.01	272			Romania	1.4	0.2%	0.08	18		
Peru	1.6	0.3%	0.06	27			Peru	1.8	0.3%	0.06	32			North Korea	1.4	0.2%	0.07	19		
North Korea	1.4	0.3%	0.07	19			North Korea	1.7	0.3%	0.07	23			Oman	1.3	0.2%	0.09	15		
Afghanistan	1.4	0.3%	0.01	113			Afghanistan	1.6	0.3%	0.01	134			Peru	1.3	0.2%	0.06	21		
Chile	1.3	0.2%	0.10	14			Chile	1.6	0.2%	0.10	16			Myanmar/Burma	1.2	0.2%	0.03	34		
Angola	1.3	0.2%	0.03	48			Angola	1.5	0.2%	0.03	57			Turkmenistan	1.1	0.2%	0.07	16		
Romania	1.3	0.2%	0.08	16			Romania	1.5	0.2%	0.08	18			Dem. Rep. of the Congo	1.1	0.2%	0.00	253		
Ghana	1.2	0.2%	0.02	58			Ghana	1.4	0.2%	0.02	69			Israel a. Palest., State o.	1.1	0.2%	0.07	17		
Mozambique	1.1	0.2%	0.01	133			Mozambique	1.4	0.2%	0.01	157			Austria	1.1	0.2%	0.07	16		
Nepal	1.1	0.2%	0.01	84			Nepal	1.3	0.2%	0.01	99			Greece	1.0	0.2%	0.06	17		
Belgium	1.1	0.2%	0.10	11			Belgium	1.3	0.2%	0.10	13			Belarus	1.0	0.2%	0.06	16		
Czechia	1.1	0.2%	0.10	11			Czechia	1.3	0.2%	0.10	13			Sudan and South Sudan	1.0	0.2%	0.02	43		
Yemen	1.1	0.2%	0.01	90			Yemen	1.3	0.2%	0.01	106			Tanzania	1.0	0.2%	0.02	58		
sum without EU	487		35				sum without EU	576		35				sum without EU	592		35			

Tab. 27: Exemplary national budgets with different global framework data⁵⁴⁵⁴ 59 countries plus the EU with the highest resulting national CO2 budgets.